

EFFECT OF SOCRATIC TEACHING METHOD ON STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN BRICK/ BLOCKLAYING AND CONCRETING IN TECHNICAL COLLEGES OF GOMBE STATE

Tafida, T.¹, Ibrahim, H. M.,² and Aliyu, A. T.³

Technology Education Department, Modibbo Adama University, Yola

Ibrahimharunamadaki02@gmail.com

Abstract

This study determined the effect of Socratic Teaching method on students' performance in brick/blocklaying and concreting trade in Government Science and Technical Colleges of Gombe State Nigeria. The study was made up of four purposes with their corresponding three research questions and three null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of alpha. The study adopted pretest, posttest nonequivalent quasi-experimental and control group design. The area of the study is Gombe state. The population of the study was 304 students while 72 NTC II BBC students made up the sample for the study. Three sampling techniques were used for the study. The subjects were separated into two groups; the experimental group I (N = 42) and the control group (N=30) using intact classes. The brick/blocklaying and Concreting Performance Test (BBCPT) was used as an instrument for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts specialized in building. The instrument was trial tested at GSTC Yola using similar BBC students but out of the researcher study area and the instrument yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.86. Three research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the three null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariates (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significant. The findings showed that; there was no significant difference in the performance of students taught brick/ blocklaying and concreting using Socratic and demonstration teaching methods $F, (df = 1,62) = 14.076, p = 1.00$, there was significant difference between males and females Brick/ blocklaying and concreting students' performance $F, (df=1, 62) = 14.076, p > 0.05$ less 0.023, there was no interaction effect of the teaching methods and gender on students' performance $F (df=1, 96) = 14.076, p > 0.05$, thus the computed p -value (**0.00**) is less than 0.05 level of significant. Recommendations were made based on the finding that Socratic teaching method improved students 'performance. The use of Socratic Method in teaching and learning of Brick/Blocklaying and concreting should be given priority. seminars, workshops and conferences should be organized on the use of Socratic teaching method in teaching Brick/ Blocklaying and concreting.

Keywords: Socratic Method of Teaching Students' Performance, Brick/Blocklaying and Concreting

Introduction

The Nigerian Technical Colleges (NTCs) are saddled with the responsibility of training students toward acquiring the appropriate vocational skills, knowledge, attitudes, habits of thoughts and qualities of character that enable them to develop their intellectual, social, physical, emotional and economic capabilities, become self-reliant and contribute to economic growth and development of their nations. Technical colleges are different from normal

secondary schools; the reason is that it emphasizes vocational education and skills acquisition rather than how to read and write (Dagogo (2014). The Nigerian Technical colleges are training grounds for individuals to acquire technical awareness and useful skills necessary for mastering a particular trade. Students who acquired First School Living Certificates are often admitted by Technical colleges for six years of vocational-technical training. The vocational and technical subjects offered in Technical colleges include; furniture making, painting, automobile mechanics, electrical and electronics repairs and installations, welding and fabrication, plumbing, woodworking, carpentry and Joinery and brick/ blocklaying and concreting.

Brick/blocklaying and concreting is offered at both intermediate and advanced levels in technical colleges. The curriculum of intermediate block laying and concreting in addition to what may be termed general education subjects such as Mathematics, English Language, Physics, Chemistry, Social studies, etc has the core trade subjects to include: Introduction to Building Construction, Concreting, Block laying, Bricklaying, Land surveying, Quantity Surveying, Technical Drawing, Building Drawing and Construction Management.

According to Oji (2012), block laying and concreting operations in the technical college curriculum involve the skills required in accomplishing given tasks in mixing of mortars by hand, Moulding of Blocks, Laying of Blocks, Rendering of Walls, Wall Tiling, Painting Top Walls and Laying of Curved Walls (Arches). It also involves the Workability Test on Concrete Slump Test, Placing of Concrete, Application of Admixture to Concrete, Compaction, Curing of Concrete and Fixing of Concrete Joint Materials. The students will perform these operations using tools and necessary equipment while teachers or examiners assess their performance based on their skills and competencies. Brick/ blocklaying and concreting operations are based on actual jobs and not pseudo or quasi jobs. The Brick/ blocklaying and concreting training should be carried out to the extent where it gives the trainee a productive ability with which he can secure and hold employment and be able to profit by it (Oji, 2012). To achieve such a level, proper instructional/training materials and skills must be utilized in the course of instruction. The use of training materials as Oji (2012) stated that it involves using materials and skills that are most appropriate and commonly available in communicating more correctly and practice the concepts of technology. These brick/Blocklaying and concreting work and practices can only be achieved through teaching and learning by the teacher using activity-based methods such as Socratic teaching method.

According to Grondin (2018), socratic teaching method of questioning is based on the practice of discipline, thoughtful dialogue. Socrates, the early Greek philosopher/teacher, believed that the disciplined practice of thoughtful questioning enabled the student to examine ideas logically and to determine the validity of those ideas. In this teaching method, the teacher professes ignorance of the topic to engage in dialogue with the students. With this "acting dumb," the student develops the fullest possible knowledge about the topic. The Socratic questioning teaching method is an effective way to explore ideas in depth. It can be used at all levels and is a helpful tool for all teachers. It can be used at different points within a unit or project. By using Socratic questioning, teachers promote independent thinking in their students and give them ownership of what they are learning. Higher-level thinking skills are present while students think, discuss debate, evaluate, and analyse content through their thinking and the thinking of those around them. These types of questions may take some practice on both the teacher and students' part since it may be a whole new teaching method (Grondin, 2018).

In the Socratic method of teaching, teachers engage students by asking questions that require generative answers. Ideally, the answers to questions are not a stopping point for thought but are instead a beginning to further analysis and research. Teachers can use the Socratic Method in a variety of subject areas and across grade levels to challenge students to examine both contemporary and historical issues (Coffey, 2014). In modelling the practice of Socrates, the teacher questions students in a manner that requires them to consider how they rationalize and respond about topics. The goal of the Socratic Method is to help students' process information and engage in a deeper understanding of topics.

Coffey (2014) stated that most importantly, the Socratic teaching method engages students in dialogue and discussion that is collaborative and open-minded as opposed to debate, which is often competitive and individualized. Ideally, teachers develop open-ended questions about texts and encourage students to use textual evidence to support their opinions and answers. In the Socratic teaching method, the teacher uses questions to guide discussion around specific learning goals. It is imperative for teachers to "establish guidelines to help students understand their roles and responsibilities" in the Socratic discussion. "Socratic questioning is a systematic process for examining the ideas, questions, and answers that form the basis of human belief. Other teaching methods such as team teaching, scaffolding, guided discovery and many more are also paramount in teaching BBC trade. The teaching methods used in teaching BBC trade have a significant effect on gender performance (males and females).

Gender refers to feminine or masculine which also means males and females brick/ blocklaying and concreting students in technical colleges. Ibrahim, Adisa, Abdulkadir and Nene (2013) defined gender as the result of socially constructed ideas about the behavior, actions and roles a particular sex performs. There is a societal feeling that technical skills are only suitable for the males and the females' counterparts are discriminated against and discouraged from such type of career. Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) also stated gender is a psychological experience of being a male or female. It has to do with personality and central components of self-concept. Unlike sex, which is concerned with, only the distinction between males and females based on biological characteristics, gender encompasses other personality attributes as roles, orientation and identity based on an individual's conceptualization of self. For instance, Singh (2010) opined that gender refers to a socio-cultural construct that connotes the differentiated roles and responsibilities of men and women in a particular society.

Tafida, et al., (2019) stated that there is a negative societal perception that technical and vocational skills acquisition is incompatible with the mother's role, at home and that girls who take to such careers have small chances to get married. These negative thoughts may influence the interest and self-confidence of the female folk and reduce their ability and motivation to opt for careers in technical skills acquisition. Eze, et al., (2015) observed that there is a general belief that boys are superior to girls in terms of cognition and logical reasoning and even in academic performance.

Students' academic performance is the extent to which the students' learners achieved the desired goals and objectives in a learning environment. As students remain the most important assets for every educational institution, so also the social and economic development of the country is directly linked with the students' academic performance. The academic performance of the students plays an important role in producing competent graduates

who will become great leaders and manpower for the country thus responsible for the country's socioeconomics development (Mushtaq & Nawa, 2012).

Jane (2014) stated that Academic performance is the quality and quantity of knowledge, skills, techniques and positive attitudes, behavior and philosophy that students achieve or acquire. This achievement is evaluated by the mark or grade that students attain in a term education cycle. The quality of grades and the number of students that pass in the various grades determine the level of academic performance. There are many factors, which account for the good or poor academic performance in technical colleges like; the quality of students admitted the type of scholastic materials available in the school and home environment, the methods of teaching, the nature of administration and teacher involvement in academic matters.

Statement of the Problem

The falling academic performance reported by Eze, et al., (2015) among others of students in technical subjects in Nigerian technical colleges is a great concern to vocational educators because of the relevance of technical education to individual self-reliance and the nation's technological and industrial development. Research studies have strongly related the academic performance of students to the methods of teaching employed by the teachers (Ganyaupfu, 2013).

The commonly used teaching method by teachers of technical subjects is the lecture method which is teacher-centered and often generates frustration and learning hitches for students. Diraso, et al., (2015) reported that information received from FCE(T) Gombe revealed that, about 86% of the students admitted into the NCE (Technical) programme had attended technical colleges in Bauchi, Gombe and Adamawa States. Yet they tend to be academically poor in the area they had been taught. This may not be unconnected with the teachers' competencies, teachers' methods of teaching, the inadequacy of training material, policy implementation, over the crowd of students in the classroom to mention among others.

Therefore, addressing the issue of low students' academic performance in technical colleges has become necessary as it affects the educational development of the state and the nation at large. It is against this background that the researcher carried out the study on the effects of Socratic and team teaching method on brick/ blocklaying and concreting students' performance in technical colleges in Gombe State with a view to a proper solution to the existing problem.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the effects of Socratic teaching method on Brick/ Blocklaying and Concreting students' performance in technical colleges in Gombe State. Specifically, the study will:

1. Compare the mean scores of BBC students taught using Socratic and demonstration teaching methods in Government technical colleges in Gombe state
2. Compare the mean scores of males and females Brick/blocklaying and Concreting students taught using the Socratic method of teaching in technical colleges in Gombe state
3. Compare the mean scores of males and females Brick/blocklaying and Concreting students using demonstration method of teaching in technical colleges in Gombe state

4. To determine the interaction effect of teaching methods and gender

Research Questions

The following research questions are raised in line with the objectives to guide the study:

1. What are the mean scores of BBC students taught using Socratic and demonstration teaching methods in Government technical colleges in Gombe state
2. What are the mean scores of males and females Brick/ Blocklaying and Concreting students taught using the Socratic method of teaching in technical colleges in Gombe state
3. What are the mean scores of males and females Brick/ Blocklaying and Concreting students taught using demonstration method of teaching in technical colleges in Gombe state

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses formulated will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁ There is no significant difference in the mean performance of Brick/ Blocklaying and Concreting students taught using Socratic and demonstration teaching methods

HO₂ There is no significant difference in the mean performance of males and females brick/ blocklaying and Concreting students taught using Socratic and demonstration teaching methods

HO₃ There was no interaction effect of teaching methods and gender

Methodology

The study adopted a pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent control group quasi-experimental research design. The quasi-experimental design investigates possible cause and effect as well as relationship between two or more variables by the application of treatment which cannot be resolve by description or mere observations. Therefore, this design is considered appropriate for this study because it uses intact class without random selection of the subjects. In this design, two groups were involved.

The area of the study is Gombe state which is located between longitude 10⁰E15⁰N and latitude12⁰E 11⁰N. The target population for the study was three hundred and four (304) NTCII BBC students of Government Science and Technical Colleges in Gombe state. The various technical colleges that formed the study cuts across the three educational zones of Gombe state include; GSTC Barunde, GSTC Kumo, GSTC Amada, GSTC Deba, GSTC Kwami, GSTC Gombe GSTC Tula.

A purposive sampling technique was used to select three core-educational Government Science and Technical Colleges in Gombe state. These are Government Science and Technical College Kwami, Government Science Technical College Barunde and Government Science and Technical College Tula. The study used intact classes of NTC II BBC students with a total number of 42 subjects in G S T C Kwami and 30 subjects in G S T C Tula made up of 72 NTC II BBC students. Brick/blocklaying and concreting Performance Test BBCPT was used as an instrument for data collection. The Bricklaying, Block laying, and Concreting Performance Test contained 50 multiple-choice items that was adopted from NABTEB past questions from 2014 - 2021. The instrument was developed from the topics in the NTCII BBC scheme of work as planned in the syllabus mainly on “brick/block

bonding and foundation in building construction”.

The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Technology Education MAU Yola and one from the Department of Technical Education FCET Gombe. The experts scrutinized the instrument in terms of face validity. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined through trial testing the instrument in Government Science and Technical College Yola which was not part of the researcher study area. The subject that were used in the pilot study comprised a total of 33 students in NTCII BBC students. The result obtained was analysed using Cronbach alpha formula and a reliability coefficient of 0.86 was obtained for the instrument.

The researcher collected the data for the study through the following procedure: The pre-test was administered prior to the commencement of the treatment to determine their academic ability level before the treatment, while the post-test was administered after the treatment. The experimental group was exposed to 6 weeks treatment using the Socratic teaching method while the control group was exposed to the same 6 weeks using demonstration teaching method (conventional method). The post test was conducted on both groups of students at the end of the training session.

The data collected was analysed using mean and standard deviation for answering the research questions 1-3 while analysis of covariate was used in testing the 3 null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Decision taking on the null hypotheses was based on comparing the computed p-value and level of significance. Where the computed p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis would be accepted and concluded that, there is no significant difference among the variables compared. On the other hand, if the computed p-value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis would be rejected and concluded that, there is significant difference among the variables compared.

Results

The results of the study were presented in tabular form based on the research Questions and hypotheses **Research Question 1.** What are the mean scores of BBC students taught using Socratic and demonstration teaching methods in Government technical colleges in Gombe state?

Table 1: Mean Scores and standard deviation of BBC Students Taught Using Socratic and Demonstration Teaching Methods

Teaching Methods	N	Pre test		Post Test	
		\bar{X}	S.D	\bar{X}	S.D
Socratic Teaching Method	42	2.93	2.02	17.96	5.85
Demonstration Teaching Method	30	4.07	1.00	17.00	4.33
Mean Difference		-1.14	1.02	0.96	2.48

The result in Table 1 revealed the mean difference of BBC students taught using Socratic and demonstration teaching methods. The groups had a pre-test mean difference of -1.14 with a corresponding standard deviation of 1.02 and a post-test mean difference of 0.96 with a corresponding standard deviation of - 2.48. This shows that Socratic teaching method has greater improvement on BBC students over demonstration teaching method. The

margin leads mean score difference between the Socratic and the demonstration teaching methods during the post-test was 0.96 favouring the Socratic Teaching Method and counting against the Socratic teaching method.

Research Question 2 What are the mean scores of males and females Brick/ Blocklaying and Concreting students taught using the Socratic method of teaching in technical colleges in Gombe state?

Table2: Mean Scores of Males and females BBC Students Taught Using Socratic Teaching Method

Gender	Teaching Method	Pre test			Post Test	
		N	\bar{X}	S.D	\bar{X}	S.D
	Socratic Teaching Method					
Males		31	2.94	1.06	17.39	4.18
Females		11	2.91	0.83	15.91	4.76
Mean Difference			0.03	0.23	1.48	-0.58

The information in Table 2 revealed the mean difference of males and females BBC students taught using Socratic teaching method. It shows the pre-test mean difference of 0.03 with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.23 and a post-test mean difference of 1.48 with a standard deviation of -0.58. The margin lead mean score between males and females BBC students is 1.48 in favour of male against the females. This shows that males performed better than female BBC students taught using Socratic teaching method.

Research Question 3. What are the mean scores of males and females Brick/ Blocklaying and Concreting students taught using demonstration method of teaching in technical colleges in Gombe state?

Table3: Mean Scores of Males and females BBC Students Taught Using Demonstration Method

Demonstration Method	Pre test			Post Test		
	N	\bar{X}	S.D	\bar{X}	S.D	
Male	25	4.24	2.15	17.96	6.37	
Female	5	3.20	0.84	18.00	2.00	
Mean Difference			1.04	1.31	-0.04	4.37

The information in Table 3 reveals the pre-test mean score difference of males and females BBC students taught using demonstration teaching method as 1.04 with a corresponding standard deviation of 1.31 and a post-test mean score difference of -0.04 with a corresponding standard deviation of 4.37. the margin lead mean score between males and females BBC students is -0.04 in favour of female against the males BBC students. This shows that female BBC students had fairly improved than their male counterparts taught using demonstration teaching method.

Hypothesis 1

HO₁ There is no significant difference in the mean performance of Brick/ Blocklaying and Concreting students taught using Socratic and demonstration teaching methods

Table 4: One way Analysis of Covariate among Socratic and Demonstration Teaching Method on BBC students' Performance

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	5905.916 ^a	6	984.319	15.249	.000
Intercept	4402.827	1	4402.827	68.206	.000
PRETST	239.099	1	239.099	3.704	.057
TEAHMETS	1817.216	2	908.608	14.076	1.000
Error	6132.397	71	64.552		
Total	60182.000	72			
Corrected Total	12038.314	71			

a. R Squared = .491 (Adjusted R Squared = .458)

The result in table 4 presented the one way Analysis of Covariate among Socratic and Demonstration Teaching Methods on BBC student performance. The $F(1, 72) = 14.076$, p -value = 1.000 tested at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the computed probability value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis was not rejected indicating that there was no significant difference among the performance of BBC students taught using Socratic and Demonstration Teaching Methods.

Hypothesis 2

HO₂ There is no significant difference in the mean performance of males and females Brick/ Blocklaying and Concreting students taught bonding and foundation using Socratic and demonstration teaching methods.

Table 5: One-way Analysis of Covariate between the Performance of Males and females BBC Students Taught Using Socratic and Demonstration Teaching Methods.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	5905.916 ^a	6	984.319	15.249	0.000
Intercept	4402.827	1	4402.827	68.206	0.000
PRETST	239.099	1	239.099	3.704	0.057
GENDER	344.881	1	344.881	5.343	0.023
Error	6132.397	69	64.552		
Total	60182.000	72			
Corrected Total	12038.314	71			

a. R Squared = .491 (Adjusted R Squared = .458)

The result in Table 5 presented one way Analysis of Covariate between males and females BBC students performance taught using Socratic and Demonstration Teaching Methods on BBC students in Government Science and Technical colleges in Gombe State. The $F(1, 72) = 5.343$, p -value = 0.023 tested at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the computed probability value is less 0.05 level of significant, hence, the null hypothesis was rejected

indicating that there was significant difference among the performance of males and females BBC students taught using Socratic and Demonstration Teaching Methods. Therefore, multiple comparisons analysis was run to precisely identify the group that is responsible for the significant difference.

Table 6: Bonferonni Multiple Comparisons Post Hoc Analysis between Males and females BBC Students Taught Using Socratic and Demonstration Teaching Methods

(I) Males and females	(J) Males and females	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Male	Female	4.548*	1.968	.023	.642	8.455
Female	Male	-4.548*	1.968	.023	-8.455	-.642

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

The result in Table 6 showed that the Male BBC students' performance were compared with their counterpart Female indicating a significant difference of 0.023 with a mean difference of 4.548*in favour of male.

Hypothesis 3

HO₃ There is no interaction effect of teaching methods and gender

Table 7: One way Analysis of Covariate on the interaction effect of teaching methods and gender

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	5905.916 ^a	6	984.319	15.249	.000
Intercept	4402.827	1	4402.827	68.206	.000
PRETST	239.099	1	239.099	3.704	.057
TEAHMETS * GENDER	657.463	1	328.731	5.093	.008
Error	6132.397	98	64.552		
Total	60182.000	72			
Corrected Total	12038.314	71			

a. R Squared = .491 (Adjusted R Squared = .458)

The result in Table 7 presented one way Analysis of Covariate on the interaction effects of teaching methods and gender, F, (1, 72) = 5.093, p - value = 0.008 tested at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the computed probability value is greater than 0.05 level of alpha; hence, the null hypothesis was accepted indicating that there was no interaction effect of teaching methods and gender.

Findings of the Study

The following findings were revealed:

1. The Socratic teaching method improves BBC students' performance higher than demonstration teaching methods with a post-test mean of 17.96.
2. The post-tests mean difference of between males and females BBC students taught using Socratic teaching method is 1.48 in favour of male against the females.
3. The post-test mean difference between males and females BBC students taught using demonstration method was -0.04 is in favour of female against the males BBC students.
4. There was no significant difference among the performance of BBC students taught using Socratic and Demonstration Teaching Methods with a probability value of 1.00.
5. There was significant difference between the performance of males and females BBC students taught using Socratic and Demonstration Teaching Methods with a probability value 0.023 in favour of Male against female.
6. There was no interaction effect of teaching methods and gender with a probability value of 0.08

Discussion of Findings

The finding revealed that Socratic teaching method improves BBC students' performance higher than demonstration teaching methods with a post-test mean of 17.96. This study is in agreement with the finding of Abrak (2015) who found out that students perform better in fine art when taught using the Socratic Method as compared to the conventional method. However, the finding of Ochogba, *et al.*, (2019) contrasted with the present finding who found that students taught with the demonstration method did better than those taught with the lecture method.

The finding reveals that the post-tests mean difference of between males and females BBC students taught using Socratic teaching method is 1.48 in favour of male against the females. This finding is in contrast with the finding of Abrak (2015) who found out that Female students are better in fine art performance when taught using the Socratic Method. However, this finding is not in agreement with the finding of Nkechi, *et al.*, (2015) who found that female students in the socratic teaching approach group achieved significantly higher than their male counterparts. The finding in research question 6 reveals that the post-test mean difference between males and females BBC students taught using demonstration method was -0.04 in favour of female against the males BBC students. The finding of the hypothesis reveals that there was no significant difference among the performance of BBC students taught using Socratic Teaching and Demonstration Teaching Methods. This finding is in contrast with the finding of Ochogba, *et al.*, (2019) who found that there was a significant difference in the mean score of students taught with the demonstration method and those taught with the lecture method in the production of wood and metal.

The finding of the hypothesis reveals that there was significant difference among the performance of males and females BBC students taught using Socratic, Team Teaching and Demonstration Teaching Methods with a probability value 0.023 in favour of Male against female. This finding is in contrast with the finding of Tafida, *et al.*, (2019) who found that there was no significant difference among the performance of males and females BBC students taught using inquiry and demonstration teaching methods. The finding of the hypothesis reveals that there was no interaction effect of teaching methods on gender with a probability value of 0.08. It is also in line with the finding of Tafida, *et al.* (2019) who found out that there was no interaction effect of teaching methods on gender.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of this study the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should emphasize on technical colleges teachers use of Socratic teaching method in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Gombe state.
2. Government should organize workshop, seminars on the use of Socratic Teaching Method in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Gombe state.
3. Government should provide the necessary facilities in the delivery of Socratic teaching method in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Gombe state.

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